

Performance Comparison Index for Image SR Models

Gökhan Koçmarlı

Faculty of Engineering / Electrical & Electronics Engineering

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Introduction

Image super-resolution enables the reconstruction of high-quality images from low-resolution inputs [Katsaggelos et al., 2007].

Current quality assessment metrics such as Structural Similarity Index (SSIM), Mean Squared Error (MSE), and PSNR have their limitations when evaluating these models effectively [Sara et al., 2019].

These metrics **focus on pixel values and statistical properties** of the images, failing to capture the overall visual quality of the output images [Arabboev et al., 2024]. To address this limitation, a **pattern-based approach** is necessary.

Research Objective

- The index shall be calculated by the **frequency components**.
- The index shall give the same result for each run **less than a 5% error**.
- The index shall be able to be used for each type of image.
- The index shall align with other metrics, such as SSIM & PSNR.
- The index shall **run faster than 20 FPS** for video processing.
- The index shall have **open-source licensing**.
- The index shall be able to be used in **two lines of code with a tool**.

Related Literature

- SSIM is meaningful statistically, but it is not necessarily how humans perceive image quality. [Nilsson and Akenine-Möller, 2020] Despite being widely used in literature, PSNR and SSIM are not perfect metrics for comparing super-resolution models [Research, 2021].
- Anwar et al. suggest that an open question exists regarding the need for a new index to align more closely with human perception and be free from pixel-based features. [Anwar et al., 2020]
- Gunawan et al. developed a technique for assessing image quality by analyzing the local harmonics of image gradients [Gunawan and Ghanbari, 2005].
- Narwaria et al. implemented a reduced-reference index that employs a division-to-bins strategy for frequencies, where higher ones are grouped into larger bins [Narwaria et al., 2012].

System Design

Realistic Constraints and Conditions

- There will be no harmful or positive effects on environmental and sustainability perspectives.
- For the public health and safety regulations, we do not provide any content that may be restricted or context that can stand as a topic of these laws.
- This study's political and social effects can be on the level of academic improvement and are limited to the area of research only.

Cost of the Design

Table 1: Cost of Design

Category	Component	Expenses
Datasets	DIV2K, Set5	Free (Academic)
Super-Resolution Models	HAT, Real-ESRGAN	Free (Apache-2.0, BSD-3.0)
GPUs	NVIDIA Tesla V100, NVIDIA GeForce 1080Ti	\$9.90 / month

Engineering Standards

Image Formatting

The proposed index and its tools can be used with the following image encoding techniques: **JPEG**, **PNG**, and **TIFF**. The implementation allows users to calculate with **all colour encoding schemes**.

Development

The proposed index is disturbed on PyPI with **continues integration** and **continues deployment** software cycle. Integration checks for PEP-8 rules and runs developed unit tests.

Project Management

In the R&D process, the **Kanban** technique is used with Plane software. The software development is tracked historically using **git version control** system.

Details of the System Design

- A tool that can upscale, downscale an image & apply common metrics for full-reference comparison.
- The performance index for the quality assessment using a pattern-based approach.
- Trained super-resolution models on the same dataset with the same amount of time: HAT and Real-ESRGAN.

Methods

We propose a new comparison index which measures the quality of images by their **harmonic structures**. We carry the basis of the problem to frequency analysis and deliver the solution **iteratively with structural similarity**.

Figure 2: Spatial and Frequency Domain Representations of Different Upscalers

The proposed performance index calculates the radius of the structurally similar sub-part of harmonics by starting from the higher frequencies and decreasing in size towards the DC component. This allows us to find the largest area where the structural similarity is above the threshold.

Figure 3: The Proposed Performance Index Traversal

Algorithm

```

IF  $SSIM(w_{grid}) > 0.95$ ,
    RETURN  $(w_{grid}/w_{fft}) \cdot 100$ 
ELSE
     $w_{grid} = w_{grid} - 2$ 
  
```

Limits – Unit

$[0, 100]$ – %

Improvements

- The calculation starts from the outermost area.
- The calculation can be done on non-square images.
- The algorithm changed to normalize the result with image size to have a global score, instead of image-specific values.
- Units are changed to percentages.
- The tool and the algorithm shared to PyPI package manager to be installed via one command: *pip install harmonicsradius*
- CI/CD pipeline is used to test on the integration level and deploy automatically to the package managers.

Results and Discussion - Initial Experiments

Frame Rate for Video Applications: 30.44 FPS

Color Experiment	SSIM	HRI95
Linear Interpolation	0.9312	49.35%
HAT SR-Model	0.8589	58.95%
Alignment Experiment	SSIM	HRI95
Linear Interpolation	0.9312	49.35%
HAT SR-Model	0.1947	58.95%
Pattern Loss Experiment	SSIM	HRI95
Linear Interpolation	0.9312	49.35%
HAT SR-Model	0.8957	0.00%

Table 2: Experiment Results

Results and Discussion - Weighted HRI95

We can achieve subject-dependent flexibility on HRI95 by dividing the frequencies into a range of bins and calculating the normalized weighted sum over those.

Figure 5: Traversal Technique for Weighted HRI95.

Results and Discussion - Channel-based HRI95

Our proposed index is mostly influenced by **the achromatic part of the image**, the Luma (Y') channel.

Table 3: HRI95 Values for Various Images in YUV Channels

Image	Y'	U	V	Mean	HRI95
Baby	43.36%	28.52%	28.52%	33.46%	43.75%
Parrot	45.14%	40.97%	39.58%	41.90%	45.14%
Butterfly	44.53%	35.16%	35.16%	38.28%	44.53%
Boy	42.86%	24.29%	33.57%	33.57%	43.57%
Woman	49.12%	26.32%	32.46%	35.97%	49.12%

Results and Discussion - Channel-based HRI95

Our proposed index is mostly influenced by, again, **the achromatic part of the image**, the brightness/value channel.

Table 4: HRI95 Values for Various Images in HSV Channels

Image	H	S	V	Mean	HRI95
Baby	7.422%	7.812%	43.36%	19.53%	43.75%
Parrot	10.42%	20.83%	42.36%	24.54%	45.14%
Butterfly	21.09%	20.31%	43.75%	28.38%	44.53%
Boy	0%	10.00%	42.86%	17.62%	43.57%
Woman	14.91%	29.83%	49.12%	31.29%	49.12%

Results and Discussion - Channel-based HRI95

Our proposed index aligns with the RGB colour scheme equally, which is expected after the experiments on HSV and YUV channels.

Table 5: HRI95 Values for Various Images in RGB Channels

Image	R	G	B	Mean	HRI95
Baby	43.75%	43.75%	43.75%	43.75%	43.75%
Parrot	44.44%	45.14%	43.75%	44.44%	45.14%
Butterfly	43.75%	44.53%	43.75%	44.01%	44.53%
Boy	43.57%	42.86%	42.86%	43.10%	43.57%
Woman	49.12%	49.12%	49.12%	49.12%	49.12%

Results and Discussion - Shifted Images

Table 6: SSIM and The Proposed Index Performance on Shift Corruption

Shift	4%	3%
HRI95	7.58%	8.57%
SSIM	0.255	0.278
Shift	2%	1%
HRI95	10.95%	33.57%
SSIM	0.371	0.687

Shifted 4%

Shifted 3%

Shifted 2%

Shifted 1%

Conclusion

This paper introduces a novel method for assessing super-resolution models using harmonic analysis. Our proposed index quantifies the similarity between harmonic magnitudes of reference and super-resolved images, providing an area-based assessment of quality. This approach overcomes the limitations of existing spatial-based metrics, which often fail to capture complex image patterns.

We demonstrate performance improvement compared to SSIM in evaluating images with spatial alterations. While our index has limitations, such as reduced effectiveness with missing image components, it represents a valuable new tool for accurate super-resolution model assessment.

Performance Comparison Index for Image Super-Resolution Models

Gökhan Koçmarlı^{1†} and Gökhan Bora Esmer^{2†}

^{1, 2}Electrical-Electronics Engineering Department, Marmara University, Başbüyük, İstanbul, 34854, Türkiye.

Contributing authors: gokhankocmarli@marun.edu.tr; bora.esmer@marmara.edu.tr;

[†]These authors contributed equally to this work.

Abstract

Image super-resolution is a critical aspect of image enhancement, facilitating the reconstruction of high-quality images from low-resolution inputs. Traditional quality assessment metrics like SSIM, MSE, and PSNR have limitations in effectively evaluating super-resolution models due to their focus on pixel values and statistical properties, overlooking overall visual quality. This article introduces a technique for comparing super-resolution models using a pattern-based approach. The proposed method evaluates image quality by analyzing the harmonics, providing a performance comparison index that surpasses traditional metrics. By focusing on the frequency domain and magnitudes of Fourier components, this technique effectively captures image features and patterns, enabling a more comprehensive assessment of super-resolution model performance.

Keywords: Super-resolution, harmonics analysis, Fourier transform, image quality assessment

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